

The Difference Between “Good” Debt and “Bad” Debt: Lessons from Jerkins

Abstract

In recent times, there has been an increasing phenomenon known as consumer debt, the practice of loaning money for the sake of necessities, such as food or clothes. This is considered irresponsible or “bad” debt. Another recent phenomenon is known as investment borrowing, the practice of loaning money for the sake of necessities such as houses or apartments. This is considered responsible or “good” debt. Considering that both kinds of borrowing are for necessities, one might be inclined to ask: What is the difference? One might initially think that food and clothes expire, but houses and land do not? Indeed, while food is not typically long-lasting, clothes historically could last generations, yes, longer than houses. Moreover, while it is true that land, as a coordinate, as 400m² for example, cannot expire, its value certainly can. The value depends on society which is known to consistently relocate, decline or expire. This text explains that, if society provided:

- 30 or 50-year jerkins loans,
- subsidies for jerkins buyers,
- speculative jerkins markets, and
- a widespread belief that “jerkins always go up”,

then jerkins, or any other arbitrary thing, would behave as a self-reinforcing asset class as well as what is currently called “real estate”.

Keywords: economics, obsolescence, asset narratives, real estate, debt, economic linguistics, jerkins, complexity

Obsolescence

A jerkin is a usually sleeveless, waist-length or hip-length, outer garment made primarily from thick leather, and, with care, could last around 60 years. Buildings, such as houses,

however, are known to last about 50 years, and are often demolished before that (O'Connor, 2004; Huuhka & Lahdensivu, 2014, Sanjo et al., 2025; Shen et al., 2013). Nevertheless, the latter is usually referred to as “real estate”, which immediately sounds self-incriminatory, for why would any product be called “real”, unless that were under question? The historical reason for this name, appears to be related to an old legal classification (Garner, 2024), not reality, which is typical for economics. Indeed, this is the origin of all the “complexity” of economics: jargon, arbitrary conventions, historical inertia and institutional mystique usually expressed as “trust the experts”. In other words, the system is complicated mostly because no one ever cleaned it up, not because its essence is difficult. Its essence, saving, lending, value exchange, is not genuinely complicated. The objective of this text was to discuss the difference between “good” and “bad” debt, but it quickly became self-evident that this is simply a scam, and therefore unworthy of discussion. Not everything is worthy of discussion. It is not any more “complex” or “intelligent” than any other scam in history, such as the snake oil scams, except:

- The “real estate” scam is on a larger, planetary scale.
- Housing is essential for human life, unlike most other scams.

If any other thing, be it leather jerkins or hamburgers, existed under the delusion that it “always goes up”, then it would always go up, until the system would inevitably fail. It is well known, both historically and in modern times, that land value too can fluctuate greatly, as societies are quite impermanent, due to “experts” who do not do their jobs. The most extreme examples are the “1€” houses which can be found in various places in the world, such as the Italian southern or insular regions (Giuffrida et al., 2020), and Russia (The Moscow Times, 2019). Of course, there exists literature that reports “real estate” crises in general, such as in Spain (Pérez, 2010), and the United States (Mallach, 2018). There is only one explanation with scientific integrity for why economists either never understood this or, more probably, chose to never reveal this: They are Jerkins.

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